

Computational tools for the analysis of the immune response of a single subject to arrays of random peptides

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An array of 150 thousand peptides with a length of 16 amino acids each was exposed to the serum of a subject, and a group of healthy controls. The subject's immunoglobulins identified a set of six peptides that distinguish his binding pattern from that of the control group. In this document, I propose a two-step pipeline for the prediction of possible autoantibodies from the knowledge of these six peptides. The first step is to search for a perfect match between all the possible sequences of seven consecutive amino acids generated by the six peptides and the human proteome. This identifies two possible matches. After verifying that the matches on the human proteins correspond to surface-exposed regions (a necessary condition for the matches to represent actual B-cell epitopes), I show how to search for compatibility between the three-dimensional arrangement of the amino acids in the query sequences, and the disposition of the amino acids on the corresponding human proteins, by using a set of two ellipsoids opportunely built on the human proteins. In the case of our subject, the first match is with a surface-exposed region of 3-ketoacyl-CoA thiolase, but it is discarded by the second step of the algorithm. The second match is with a region of Centrosomal protein of 164 kDa that is not accessible to immunoglobulins and therefore discarded with no further analysis. I then repeated the same analysis with matches of only 6 amino acids. But no cross-reactive epitopes were found. This pipeline is amenable to further automatization, especially in the last step which at present consists of a qualitative comparison made by the user, based on three-dimensional, interactive plots.

1 Introduction

The use of a collection of thousands of short random peptides coated to a plate has been recently proposed as an efficient way to study the response of B cells to cancer (1), infections (2), immunization (3), and autoimmunity (4). This same method has been applied to ME/CFS patients and it has shown the potential of identifying an immunosignature that can differentiate patients from controls (5), (6). But what about the antigens eliciting the antibody profile? Given a set of peptides one's antibodies react to, a possible solution for interpreting the data is to use these peptides as query sequences in a BLAST search against proteins from all the microorganisms known to infect humans and proteins from the human proteome. This has been done for ME/CFS, and the analysis led to several matches among proteins from bacteria, viruses, endogenous retroviruses, and human proteins (5). There are several problems with this approach, though. First of all, the number of random peptides usually used in these arrays is not representative of the variety of possible epitopes of the same length present in nature. If we consider the paper by Günther O.P. and colleagues, for instance, they used an array of about 10^5 random peptides with a length of 12 amino acids each, with the number of all the possible peptides of the same length being $20^{12} \sim 4 \cdot 10^{15}$. This means that many potential epitopes one has antibodies to are not represented in the array. Another important limitation is that B-cell epitopes are mainly conformational ones, which means that they are assembled by the folding of the proteins they belong to (7, 8), the consequence of this being that the subset of random peptides one's serum reacts to are linear epitopes that *mimic* conformational ones (they are often called *mimotopes*) (9). This means that a BLAST search of these peptides against a library of proteins from pathogens can lead to completely misleading results.

2 Searching for linear matches within the human proteome

In this section, I present an R script that searches for linear matches (of a fixed length) between the peptides from the immunological analysis, and the proteins included in the human proteome.

2.1 Generation of the query sequences

My serum has been analyzed by measuring its reactivity to an array of 150.000 peptides with a length of 16 random amino acids (plus four amino acids used to link the peptides to the plate). Residues Threonine (T), Isoleucine (I), and Cysteine (C) were not included. This analysis was performed as described in (9). An anti-human-IgG antibody was employed as a secondary antibody. My serum identified a set of 6 peptides that differentiate my immunological response from that of healthy controls. The six peptides, which will be referred to as query sequences, are reported in Table 1.

1	ALHHRHVGLRVQYDSG
2	ALHRHRVGPQLQSSGS
3	ALHRRQRVLSPLVGAS
4	ALHRVLSEQDPQLVLS
5	ALHVRVLSQKRPLQLG
6	ALHLHRHVLESQVNSL

Table 1. My immunosignature, as detected by an array of 150.000 random peptides 20-amino-acid long, four of which are used for fixing them to the plate and are not included here.

The purpose of the following analysis is to search for a possible self-epitope that might interact with the IgGs that selected the peptides in Table 1. To overcome the limitations enumerated at the end of the previous paragraph I have decided to search within the database of viral proteins for exact matches of the length of 7 amino acids. The choice for this length is grounded on the following considerations. A survey of a set of validated B cell epitopes found that the average B cell epitope has a linear stretch of 5 amino acids (7); according to another similar work, the average linear epitope within a conformational one has a length of 4-7 amino acids (8). To filter the matches and to reduce the number of matches due to chance, I opted for the upper limit of this length. I excluded longer matches to limit the number of mimotopes for conformational epitopes. Moreover, I decided to look only for perfect matches (excluding the possibility of gaps and substitutions) so to simplify the analysis. To generate the set of all the possible stretches of 7 consecutive amino acids from the 6 peptides of the immunosignature (Table 1), I wrote the following lines of code in Octave. The output is in the format used for the input of BLAST.

```
% file_name: immunosignature.m
%
clear all
pkg load io
n = 8;
peptides = cell();
peptides{1} = "ALHHRHVGLRVQYDSG";
peptides{2} = "ALHRRVGPQLQSSGS";
peptides{3} = "ALHRRQVLSPVLGAS";
peptides{4} = "ALHRVLSEQDPQLVLS";
peptides{5} = "ALHVRVLSQKRPLQLG";
peptides{6} = "ALHLHRHVLESQVNSL";
%
mers = cell();
k = 0;
for i=1:6
    for j=1:(16-n+1)
        k = k+1;
        mers{k} = substr(char(peptides{i}),j,n);
    endfor
endfor
%
mers2 = cell();
h = 0;
for i=1:k
    h = h+1;
    mers2{h} = mers{i};
    h = h+1;
    mers2{h} = ">";
endfor
file_name = 'mers.csv'
cell2csv (file_name, mers2, " ")
```

2.2 Searching matches within the human proteome

The 60 linear stretches of 7 consecutive amino acids, generated from the six peptides of Table 1 are compared with the human proteome [UP000005640](#), in search of identical matches. This task is performed by the following R script, which reads the six peptides and a FASTA file

containing the human proteome. We find two matches (Table 2), one between the first peptide of the immunosignature (from position 5 to 12) and the enzyme 3-ketoacyl-CoA thiolase ([P42765](#), from position 71 to 78) and the other between the third peptide and the Centrosomal protein of 164 kDa ([Q9UPV0](#), from position 428 to 435). The two stretches are RHVGLRV and VLSPVLG, respectively.

Match	Query sequence (position)	Human protein (position)	Description
RHVGLRV	1 (5-12)	P42765 (71-78)	3-ketoacyl-CoA thiolase
VLSPVLG	3 (8-15)	Q9UPV0 (428-435)	Centrosomal protein of 164 kDa

Table 2. Matches between the query sequences and the human proteome [UP000005640](#).

```
# file name: immunosignature_human
#
# Rome, June 12th, 2023
#
start.time <- Sys.time() # we use it to compute execution time
library("seqinr") # it contains read.fasta()
setwd("C:/Users/macpa/OneDrive/Appunti/Immunologia/Immunosignature") # set the directory
mer<-7 # the length of the peptides considered
#
#-----
# We now store the human proteome in a list called hsprot. The structure is such
# that hsprot[[i]] is an array containing the i-th protein, and hsprot[[i]][j]
# contains its j-th amino acid. Moreover, attr(hsprot[[i]],"name") gives the
# name of the i-th protein and attr(hsprot [[i]],"Annot") gives further
# information.
#-----
#
hsprot<-read.fasta(file = "UP000005640_9606.fasta")
n<-length(hsprot) # number of human proteins
#
#-----
# We now store the query sequences in an array each, the array are included in a
# list, same structure as above. The query sequences are in fasta format.
#-----
#
peptides<-read.fasta(file = "immunosignature.fasta")
nq<-length(peptides) # number of query sequences
lq<-length(peptides[[1]]) # length of the query sequences
#
#-----
# We search for peptides of mer amino acids shared by the query sequences and
# the sequences included in the human proteome
#-----
#
matches<-c() # It will contain the peptides found by the search
query<-c() # It will contain the number of the peptides containing a hit
startq<-c() # It is the starting position of the match on the peptide
protein<-c() # It will contain the number of the human proteins containing a hit
start<-c() # It will contain the starting position of the match on the human protein
found<-0 # the number of matches
for (i in 1:nq) { # select the query sequence
```

```

for (j in 1:(lq-mer+1)) { # select the peptide of mer aa within the query sequence
  temp_q<-peptides[[i]][j:(j+mer-1)] # store the peptide of mer aa form the query sequence
  temp_q<-paste(temp_q,collapse="") # from array to string
  for (k in 1:n) { # select the human protein
    l<-length(hsprot[[k]]) # length of the human protein
    if (l>=mer) {
      for (p in 1:(l-mer+1)) { # select the peptide of mer aa within the human protein
        temp<-hsprot[[k]][p:(p+mer-1)] # store the peptide of mer aa from the human protein
        temp<-paste(temp,collapse="") # from array to string
        if (temp_q==temp) {
          found<-found+1 # the ordinal number of the match
          matches[found]<-toupper(temp_q) # the matching peptide, in uppercase
          query[found]<-i # the ordinal number of the query sequence containing the match
          startq[found]<-j # the starting position of the match on the query sequence
          protein[found]<-k # the ordinal number of the human protein containing the match
          start[found]<-p # the starting position of the match on the human peptide
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
#
#-----
# Output
#-----
#
output<-data.frame(sequence=matches,protein=protein,start_p=start,stop_p=(start+mer),
  query=query,start_q=startq,stop_q=(startq+mer))
file_name<-paste(as.character(mer),"_mer_matches_human.csv",sep="")
write.csv(output, file = file_name, col.names=T)
#
#-----
# Execution time
#-----
#
end.time <- Sys.time()
time.taken <- end.time - start.time
time.taken

```

2.3 Acquiring the structure of the peptides

We assume that the peptides coated on the plate of the array are not denaturated. Therefore we need a prediction of their tertiary structure. I used the prediction by AlphaFold2 (10), provided by [Neurosnap](#). Default settings were employed and only the rank 1 structure was considered. The structures were downloaded in PDB format. The 3D arrangement of the amino acids of peptide 1 can be seen in Figure 7.

2.4 Acquiring the structure of the proteins

To study the position of the linear peptide 71-78 of protein [P42765](#), I considered its experimental structure [4c2j](#) (11), I downloaded it in .ent format from the Uniprot website, then I converted it to ASN1 data using VAST search page ([R](#)) and hence read with Cn3D (12). This protein is encoded by [ACAA2](#) and it catalyzes the last step of the mitochondrial fatty acid beta-

oxidation. The enzyme is expressed mainly by the liver, kidneys, adipose tissue, and small intestine. The position of the peptide can be seen in Figure 1, where I reported both the A subunit alone and the A subunit entangled with the other three identical subunits of the enzyme. It can be seen on the left of Figure 1 that the linear stretch at positions 71-78 on subunit A (purple) is partially buried by subunit B (blue), while it is completely exposed when subunit A is not bound to subunit B.

Figure 1. Enzyme 3-ketoacyl-CoA thiolase (experimental structure [4c2j](#)). The 7-mer peptide 71-78 of subunit A is highlighted in yellow. In the tetrameric ensemble (left), the 7-mer is partially buried by subunit B.

Figure 2. ElliPro predicts that the positions 71-77 of chain A of the enzyme 3-ketoacyl-CoA thiolase (experimental structure [4c2j](#)) are included in both a linear epitope of chain A only (left) and a big conformational epitope involving both chain A and chain B (right).

Since the 7-mer peptide is at least partially surface exposed, there is a possibility that it is part of a B-cell epitope of the enzyme. And if we examine the linear epitopes of chain A of the

enzyme predicted by ElliPro (13), we find that peptide 71-84 is such an epitope, with a score of 0.73 (Figure 2, left); not only that, residues A:R71, A:G74, A:L75, A:V77 are predicted to be part of a big conformational epitope, involving both chain A and chain B (Figure 2, right). In the case of protein [Q9UPV0](#), there is no complete experimental structure, therefore I used a predicted structure, calculated by AlphaFold. The region including the sequence 428-435 is not included in any of the epitopes predicted by ElliPro for this protein and that region, despite on the surface of the protein, falls in a depression that is likely not accessible to IgGs.

Figure 3. Centrosomal protein of 164 kDa, structure predicted by AlphaFold and plotted by Cn3D. The stretch 428-435 is highlighted in yellow.

3 Searching for cross-reactive epitopes in the protein, selected by the linear matches

In this section I present a software that provides a visual plotting of the region of the protein around the linear match with the peptide; this plotting can be used to verify whether this region is surface exposed and the peptide is a reasonable mimotope of it. The detailed discussion that follows is applied to the study of the possible cross-reactivity between peptide 1 and the subunit A of protein P42765.

3.1 Acquiring some preliminary data

Before reading the peptide and the protein, we need a few data, such as the diameter of each amino acid, expressed in Å, and the masses of principal elements. The radii are taken from (14). The subroutine that reads this set of data is the following.

```
function [aa_radii,aa_name,atom_mass,atom_name] = input ()
%
% It reads the radii (Angstrom) for each one of the standard amino acids, from
% NEPRE: a Scoring Function for Protein Structures based on Neighbourhood Preference
% 2018, DOI:10.1101/463554
%
file_name = "AA_radii.xlsx";
[filetype, sh_names, fformat, nmranges] = xlsinfo (file_name);
sheet = sh_names(3);
```

```

strn = char(sh_names(1,2));
strn = substr(strn,5); % number of aa as a string
range = strcat("A1:B",strn);
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
aa_radii = num;
aa_name = text;
%
% It reads the mass (in atomic mass units, amu) of common elements
%
file_name = "common_elements.xlsx";
[filetype, sh_names, fformat, nmranges] = xlsfinfo (file_name);
sheet = sh_names(9);
strn = char(sh_names(1,2));
strn = substr(strn,5); % number of atoms as a string
range = strcat("A1:B",strn);
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
atom_mass = num;
atom_name = text;
endfunction

```

3.2 Analysis of the protein

3.2.1 Acquiring the protein

In this context, we use for the coordinates of the protein a modified PDB format. It is obtained by removing all the lines of a standard PDB file that do not contain the coordinates of the atoms of the protein. The file is then converted into xlsx format. Below you can see the first lines of the xlsx file used for protein P42765, structure 4C2J (Table 3). The second column contains the ordinal number of the atoms, starting from the azote of the first amino acid of the primary structure, from the N-terminus to the C-terminus. Note that the atoms are indicated according to their role within the amino acid: so CA is the carbon α , CB is the carbon β , and so forth. In the last column, on the contrary, the atoms are indicated only with the symbol of the corresponding element. The fourth column contains the three-letter symbol of the amino acid, then we have the number of the amino acid within the sequence of the protein, then the three coordinates of each atom. The subroutine that reads the coordinates is the following one. The protein is then plotted, with the amino acids represented by spheres with the proper radius, as in Figure 4.

```

function [atom_n_p,atom_name_p,atom_name_aa_p,aa_name_p,X,Y,Z] = input_sequence (protein_name)
%
% It reads the number of atoms of the peptide
%
file_name = strcat(protein_name,".xlsx");
[filetype, sh_names, fformat, nmranges] = xlsfinfo (file_name);
sheet = sh_names{1};
strn = char(sh_names(1,2));
strn = substr(strn,5); % number of atoms as a string
atom_n_p = str2num(strn); % number of atoms as a number
%
% It read the number of the atoms
%
%range = strcat("B1:B",strn);
%[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);

```

```

%atom_n_p = num;
%
% It read the atoms
%
range = strcat("L1:L",strn);
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
atom_name_p = text;
%
% It read the atoms of the amino acid
%
range = strcat("C1:C",strn);
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
atom_name_aa_p = text;
%
% It read the amino acids
%
range = strcat("D1:D",strn);
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
aa_name_p = text;
%
% It read the coordinates
%
range = strcat("G1:G",strn);
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
X = num;
range = strcat("H1:H",strn);
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
Y = num;
range = strcat("I1:I",strn);
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
Z = num;
endfunction

```

ATOM	1	N	HIS	A	0	1.98	-84.302	42.007	1	45.8	N
ATOM	2	CA	HIS	A	0	3.215	-83.643	42.563	1	43.99	C
ATOM	3	C	HIS	A	0	4.336	-83.695	41.508	1	41.95	C
ATOM	4	O	HIS	A	0	4.519	-84.708	40.827	1	38.45	O
ATOM	5	CB	HIS	A	0	3.643	-84.215	43.949	1	48.39	C
ATOM	6	CG	HIS	A	0	4.978	-83.718	44.461	1	55.37	C
ATOM	7	ND1	HIS	A	0	5.396	-82.406	44.345	1	57.13	N
ATOM	8	CD2	HIS	A	0	5.971	-84.359	45.132	1	57.32	C
ATOM	9	CE1	HIS	A	0	6.592	-82.265	44.89	1	51.5	C
ATOM	10	NE2	HIS	A	0	6.96	-83.435	45.382	1	58.98	N
ATOM	11	N	MET	A	1	5.036	-82.578	41.34	1	35.07	N
ATOM	12	CA	MET	A	1	6.156	-82.492	40.421	1	36.92	C
ATOM	13	C	MET	A	1	7.208	-81.61	41.071	1	33.86	C
ATOM	14	O	MET	A	1	7.018	-80.397	41.213	1	30.57	O
ATOM	15	CB	MET	A	1	5.724	-81.921	39.059	1	44.94	C
ATOM	16	CG	MET	A	1	6.842	-81.894	38.002	1	57.67	C
ATOM	17	SD	MET	A	1	6.33	-81.262	36.362	1	71.38	S
ATOM	18	CE	MET	A	1	5.279	-82.586	35.766	1	73.11	C


```

endfor
%
% We assign the mass to each atom of the protein
%
for i=1:atom_n_p
  for j=1:length(atom_name)
    if (atom_name_p{i}==atom_name{j})
      atom_mass_p(i) = atom_mass(j);
    endif
  endfor
endfor
%
% We find the center of mass of each amino acid
%
aa_n_p = counter(atom_n_p,2); % the number of aas of the sequence
i=1;
for j=1:aa_n_p % we set the amino acid on the sequence
  Xc(j) = 0;
  Yc(j) = 0;
  Zc(j) = 0;
  aa_mass_p(j) = 0;
  k = 0;
  while (counter(i,2)==j)
    Xc(j) = Xc(j) + X(i)*atom_mass_p(i);
    Yc(j) = Yc(j) + Y(i)*atom_mass_p(i);
    Zc(j) = Zc(j) + Z(i)*atom_mass_p(i);
    aa_mass_p(j) = aa_mass_p(j) + atom_mass_p(i);
    k = k + 1; % we move to the next atom of the amino acid
    if (i+1>atom_n_p)
      break
    endif
    i = i + 1; % we move to the next atom of the protein
  endwhile
  % i - ordinal number of the first atom of amino acid j+1
  % j - ordinal number of the amino acid just examined
  % k - number of atoms on amino acid j
  Xc(j) = Xc(j)/aa_mass_p(j);
  Yc(j) = Yc(j)/aa_mass_p(j);
  Zc(j) = Zc(j)/aa_mass_p(j);
endfor
%
%-----
% We find the radius of each amino acid of the protein
%-----
%
aa_name_p_2 = cell();
for j=1:aa_n_p % we set the amino acid on the sequence
  for i=1:atom_n_p
    if (counter(i,2)==j) % we search for the first atom of amino acid j
      for k=1:length(aa_radrii) % we set the amino acid on the list of the standard aas
        v=aa_name_p{i}==aa_name{k};
        if (v(1)+v(2)+v(3)==3)
          aa_radrii_p(j) = aa_radrii(k);
          aa_name_p_2{j} = aa_name{k};
        endif
      endfor
    endif
  endfor
  break % we exit the FOR statement and move on the following amino acid

```

```

endif
endfor
endfor
endfunction

```


Figure 5. Distribution of the distance between the centers of mass of two consecutive amino acids of the primary structure of subunit A of protein P42765, structure 4C2J.

Once we have the centers of mass, it might be interesting to define the distribution of the distances between amino acids that are adjacent along the primary structure of the protein. The distances are acquired by the following lines of code:

```

for j=1:aa_n_p - 1
  dist(j) = sqrt( (Xc(j+1)-Xc(j))^2 + (Yc(j+1)-Yc(j))^2 + (Zc(j+1)-Zc(j))^2 );
endfor

```

The distribution of these distances, for the subunit A of protein P42765, structure 4C2J, can be seen in Figure 5.

3.2.3 Moments of inertia of the protein

Let the initial reference system for the peptide be $O; X, Y, Z$. We then calculate the center of mass of the protein by using the following equations:

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad X_{C_p} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_{aa}} X_c^{(k)} m^{(k)}}{\mathcal{M}_p}, \quad Y_{C_p} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_{aa}} Y_c^{(k)} m^{(k)}}{\mathcal{M}_p}, \quad Z_{C_p} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_{aa}} Z_c^{(k)} m^{(k)}}{\mathcal{M}_p}$$

where $\mathcal{M}_p = \sum_{k=1}^{n_{aa}} m^{(k)}$ is the total mass of the peptide, $m^{(k)}$ is the mass of the k^{th} amino acid of the peptide, n_{aa} is the number of amino acids in the peptide. We define the reference system $C_p; \xi, \eta, \zeta$ with the origin on the center of mass of the protein and with the axes oriented as the

axes of $O; x, y, z$. The relationship between the coordinates of these two reference systems is obviously

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_p} \\ Y_{C_p} \\ Z_{C_p} \end{bmatrix}$$

We then calculate the moments of inertia of the protein with respect to $C_p; \xi, \eta, \zeta$ by computing the following sums:

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad \begin{cases} J_\xi = \sum_i m_i (\eta_c^{(i)2} + \zeta_c^{(i)2}) \\ J_\eta = \sum_i m_i (\xi_c^{(i)2} + \zeta_c^{(i)2}) \\ J_\zeta = \sum_i m_i (\xi_c^{(i)2} + \eta_c^{(i)2}) \\ J_{\xi\eta} = \sum_i m_i \xi_c^{(i)} \eta_c^{(i)} \\ J_{\xi\zeta} = \sum_i m_i \xi_c^{(i)} \zeta_c^{(i)} \\ J_{\eta\zeta} = \sum_i m_i \eta_c^{(i)} \zeta_c^{(i)} \end{cases}$$

Then we build the matrix of inertia with respect to $C_p; \xi, \eta, \zeta$:

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad M_p = \begin{bmatrix} J_\xi & -J_{\xi\eta} & -J_{\xi\zeta} \\ -J_{\xi\eta} & J_\eta & -J_{\eta\zeta} \\ -J_{\xi\zeta} & -J_{\eta\zeta} & J_\zeta \end{bmatrix}$$

This is the subroutine that calculates the moments of inertia.

```
function [protein_mass,Xic,Etac,Zetac,M,Xcp,Ycp,Zcp] = moments_of_inertia (aa_n_p,aa_mass_p,Xc,Yc,Zc)
%
% search for the mass of the protein
%
protein_mass = 0;
for j=1:aa_n_p
    protein_mass = protein_mass + aa_mass_p(j);
endfor
%
% search for the center of mass of the protein
%
Xcp = 0;
Ycp = 0;
Zcp = 0;
for j=1:aa_n_p
    Xcp = Xcp + Xc(j)*aa_mass_p(j);
    Ycp = Ycp + Yc(j)*aa_mass_p(j);
    Zcp = Zcp + Zc(j)*aa_mass_p(j);
endfor
Xcp = Xcp/protein_mass;
Ycp = Ycp/protein_mass;
Zcp = Zcp/protein_mass;
%
```

```

% We translate the system of coordinates so that its center is Xcp,Ycp,Zcp
%
Xic = Xc - Xcp;
Etac = Yc - Ycp;
Zetac = Zc - Zcp;
%
% We calculate the central moments of inertia
%
J_xi = 0;
J_eta = 0;
J_zeta = 0;
J_xi_eta = 0;
J_xi_zeta = 0;
J_eta_zeta = 0;
for j=1:aa_n_p
    J_xi = J_xi + aa_mass_p(j)*( Etac(j)^2 + Zetac(j)^2 );
    J_eta = J_eta + aa_mass_p(j)*( Xic(j)^2 + Zetac(j)^2 );
    J_zeta = J_zeta + aa_mass_p(j)*( Xic(j)^2 + Etac(j)^2 );
    J_xi_eta = J_xi_eta + aa_mass_p(j)*Xic(j)*Etac(j);
    J_xi_zeta = J_xi_zeta + aa_mass_p(j)*Xic(j)*Zetac(j);
    J_eta_zeta = J_eta_zeta + aa_mass_p(j)*Etac(j)*Zetac(j);
endfor
%
% we build the protein matrix of inertia with respect to XiC, Etac, Zetac
%
M(1,1:3) = [J_xi, -J_xi_eta, -J_xi_zeta];
M(2,1:3) = [-J_xi_eta, J_eta, -J_eta_zeta];
M(3,1:3) = [-J_xi_zeta, -J_eta_zeta, J_zeta];
endfunction

```


Figure 6. Plotting of the tertiary structure of subunit A of protein P42765, structure 4C2J. Each amino acid is represented by a dot with the center in its center of mass, the linear stretch of interest is highlighted in yellow, and the ellipsoid including a proportion F of the mass of the protein is also plotted in grades of green. F = 0.2 in this case.

3.2.4 Ellipsoid of inertia of the protein: primary ellipsoid

The equation of the central ellipsoid of inertia of the protein with respect to C_p ; ξ, η, ζ is

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad [\xi \quad \eta \quad \zeta] \begin{bmatrix} J_\xi & -J_{\xi\eta} & -J_{\xi\zeta} \\ -J_{\xi\eta} & J_\eta & -J_{\eta\zeta} \\ -J_{\xi\zeta} & -J_{\eta\zeta} & J_\zeta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = \chi$$

or also $J_\xi \xi^2 + J_\eta \eta^2 + J_\zeta \zeta^2 - 2J_{\xi\eta} \xi \eta - 2J_{\eta\zeta} \eta \zeta - 2J_{\xi\zeta} \xi \zeta = \chi$. The scaling factor χ is chosen to have the smaller ellipsoid that includes a proportion F of the entire mass of the protein. This determination can be easily accomplished by considering that if P is a point on the surface of the ellipsoid and if α, β, γ are the direction cosines of $\overrightarrow{C_p P}$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\overrightarrow{C_p P}|^2 (J_\xi \alpha^2 + J_\eta \beta^2 + J_\zeta \gamma^2 - 2J_{\xi\eta} \alpha \beta - 2J_{\xi\zeta} \alpha \gamma - 2J_{\eta\zeta} \beta \gamma) &= \chi \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow |\overrightarrow{C_p P}| &= \frac{\chi}{J_\xi \alpha^2 + J_\eta \beta^2 + J_\zeta \gamma^2 - 2J_{\xi\eta} \alpha \beta - 2J_{\xi\zeta} \alpha \gamma - 2J_{\eta\zeta} \beta \gamma} \end{aligned}$$

That said, let P_i the center of mass of the i^{th} amino acid of the peptide. We search for the smaller value χ such that all the amino acids that satisfy the following relation for a given value of χ , sum up to a mass that is equal to the protein mass multiplied by F .

$$|\overrightarrow{C_p P_i}| \leq \frac{\chi}{J_s \alpha^2 + J_t \beta^2 + J_v \gamma^2 - 2J_{st} \alpha \beta - 2J_{sv} \alpha \gamma - 2J_{tv} \beta \gamma}$$

We perform this calculation starting with $\chi = 0$ and increasing its value by a small fraction (1/100, for instance) of the maximum value of

$$|\overrightarrow{C_p P_i}| (J_\xi \alpha^2 + J_\eta \beta^2 + J_\zeta \gamma^2 - 2J_{\xi\eta} \alpha \beta - 2J_{\xi\zeta} \alpha \gamma - 2J_{\eta\zeta} \beta \gamma)$$

calculated for the centers of mass of all the amino acids of the protein. This job is performed by the following subroutine. A figure with the protein (with amino acids represented this time as dots) and of the ellipsoid, is then generated, as in Figure 6. This ellipsoid is referred to as *primary ellipsoid*.

```
function [Chi,selection,product_Chi] =...
ellipsoid_of_inertia(aa_n_p,Xic,Etac,Zetac,F,M,steps,aa_mass_p,protein_mass)
%
% Given a value Chi, the distance of the point P of the ellipsoid from the origin
% C is given by the square root of Chi/J_r, where J_r is the moment of inertia
% around the axis r defined by CP. We calculate Chi such that the ellipsoid contains
% a fraction F of the mass of the protein.
%
% Calculate the distance from the origin, the angular coefficients, and
% the J_r for each aa
%
```

```

for j=1:aa_n_p
aa_dist(j) = sqrt(Xic(j)^2 + Etac(j)^2 + Zetac(j)^2);
alpha(j) = Xic(j)/aa_dist(j);
beta(j) = Etac(j)/aa_dist(j);
gamma(j) = Zetac(j)/aa_dist(j);
v1 = [alpha(j), beta(j), gamma(j)];
v2 = transpose(v1);
J_r(j) = v1*M*v2;
product_Chi(j) = (aa_dist(j)^2)*J_r(j);
endfor
%
% we build an interval for Chi, from zero to the highest value in product_Chi
%
delta_Chi = max(product_Chi)/steps;
for i=1:steps
Chi(i) = i*delta_Chi;
endfor
%
% we search for the value of Chi such that the ellipsoid includes F of the total mass
%
for i=1:steps % set the value of Chi
mass_inside(i) = 0;
for j=1:aa_n_p % set the amino acid
if (product_Chi(j)<=Chi(i))
mass_inside(i) = mass_inside(i) + aa_mass_p(j);
endif
endfor
F_inside(i) = mass_inside(i)/protein_mass;
endfor
%
% we select the ellipsoid including F of the protein mass
%
for i=1:steps
if (F_inside(i)>=F)
selection = i;
break
endif
endfor
endfunction

```

3.2.5 Central axes of inertia of the protein

The search for the central axes of inertia of the protein can be accomplished by diagonalization of the matrix of inertia. More precisely, let Λ be the diagonal matrix such that

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad \begin{bmatrix} J_{\xi} & -J_{\xi\eta} & -J_{\xi\zeta} \\ -J_{\xi\eta} & J_{\eta} & -J_{\eta\zeta} \\ -J_{\xi\zeta} & -J_{\eta\zeta} & J_{\zeta} \end{bmatrix} = V_p \Lambda_p V_p^T$$

then we have that

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad \Lambda_p = \begin{bmatrix} J_a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & J_b & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & J_c \end{bmatrix}$$

is the diagonal matrix whose diagonal elements are the major semi-axes of the central ellipsoid of inertia with respect to the reference system C_p ; a, b, c ; and it is such that

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix} = V_p^T \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = V_p \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix}$$

In other words, the columns of V_p^T are the coordinates of the unit vectors of C_p ; ξ, η, ζ with respect to C_p ; a, b, c , while the columns of V_p are the coordinates with respect to C_p ; ξ, η, ζ of the unit vectors of C_p ; a, b, c . In other words¹, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad \hat{a} = [\hat{\xi} \quad \hat{\eta} \quad \hat{\zeta}] V_p \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{b} = [\hat{\xi} \quad \hat{\eta} \quad \hat{\zeta}] V_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{c} = [\hat{\xi} \quad \hat{\eta} \quad \hat{\zeta}] V_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Note that these components are the same as those expressed with respect to $O; X, Y, Z$, in other words:

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad \hat{a} = [\hat{X} \quad \hat{Y} \quad \hat{Z}] V_p \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{b} = [\hat{X} \quad \hat{Y} \quad \hat{Z}] V_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{c} = [\hat{X} \quad \hat{Y} \quad \hat{Z}] V_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The matrices Λ_p and V_p are determined by the subroutine `central_axes`, reported below, which also determines the coordinates of all the centers of mass of the amino acids, with respect to C_p ; a, b, c .

```
function [semi_axis_A,semi_axis_B,semi_axis_C,V,lambda,Ac,Bc,Cc] =...
central_axes(aa_n_p,M,Chi,selection,Xic,Etac,Zetac)
%
%-----
% We search for the central axes of inertia, for the semi-major axes of the
% ellipsoid, and for the coordinates of the amino acids with respect to the
% central axes
%-----
%
[V, lambda] = eig (M); % lambda is the diagonal matrix of M such that V*lambda*transpose(V) = M
%
% We calculate the coordinates with respect to the central axes of the CoMs of the aas
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
temp = transpose(V)*transpose([Xic(j),Etac(j),Zetac(j)]);
Ac(j) = temp(1);
Bc(j) = temp(2);
Cc(j) = temp(3);
endfor
%
% We calculate the semi-major axes of the ellipsoid
%
semi_axis_A = sqrt(Chi(selection)/lambda(1,1));
semi_axis_B = sqrt(Chi(selection)/lambda(2,2));
semi_axis_C = sqrt(Chi(selection)/lambda(3,3));
endfunction
```

¹ In this document \hat{X} is the unit vector of the X axis. And so forth.

The function is called with the line:

```
[semi_axis_A,semi_axis_B,semi_axis_C,Vp,lambda_p,Ac,Bc,Cc] = ...
central_axes(aa_n_p,Mp,Chi,selection,Xic,Etac,Zetac)
```


Figure 7. The peptide query-1-rank-1, represented with the linear match highlighted in yellow, the reference system R' : O' ; p, q, r in red, the reference system R'' : C_{pe} ; s, t, v in blu, and the reference system R''' : C_{pe} ; α, β, γ in yellow.

3.3 Analysis of the peptide

3.3.1 The reference system defined by the match sequence

Let the initial reference system for the peptide be $R: O; x, y, z$. We consider a new reference system, $R': O'; p, q, r$, with the origin in the center of mass of the first amino acid of the linear match within the peptide. Let the unit vectors of R' be defined by the positions of the centers of mass of the first three amino acids of the match, according to the following algorithm. The coordinates of the first unit vector of R' are given by

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad \hat{p} = \frac{(x_c^{(i_2)} - x_c^{(i_1)})\hat{e}_1 + (y_c^{(i_2)} - y_c^{(i_1)})\hat{e}_2 + (z_c^{(i_2)} - z_c^{(i_1)})\hat{e}_3}{\sqrt{(x_c^{(i_2)} - x_c^{(i_1)})^2 + (y_c^{(i_2)} - y_c^{(i_1)})^2 + (z_c^{(i_2)} - z_c^{(i_1)})^2}}$$

where $x_c^{(i_1)}, y_c^{(i_1)}, z_c^{(i_1)}$ are the coordinates with respect to R of the first amino acid of the match and $x_c^{(i_2)}, y_c^{(i_2)}, z_c^{(i_2)}$ are those of the second amino acid. We then define \hat{q} , the second unit vector of R' , as the one orthogonal to the plane defined by the first three amino acids of the match; more precisely, we write

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad \hat{q} = \frac{\hat{p} \times \left((x_c^{(i_3)} - x_c^{(i_2)}) \hat{e}_1 + (y_c^{(i_3)} - y_c^{(i_2)}) \hat{e}_2 + (z_c^{(i_3)} - z_c^{(i_2)}) \hat{e}_3 \right)}{\left| \hat{p} \times \left((x_c^{(i_3)} - x_c^{(i_2)}) \hat{e}_1 + (y_c^{(i_3)} - y_c^{(i_2)}) \hat{e}_2 + (z_c^{(i_3)} - z_c^{(i_2)}) \hat{e}_3 \right) \right|}$$

The third unit vector is at this point defined by

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad \hat{r} = \hat{p} \times \hat{q}$$

The reference system R' can be seen in Figure 7, along with a representation of the peptide. The matrix of the passage of coordinates from R' to R is calculated by the following subroutine.

```
function [Mat] = reference_system (Xc1,Yc1,Zc1,Xc2,Yc2,Zc2,Xc3,Yc3,Zc3);
    Mat(1,1) = Xc2-Xc1;
    Mat(2,1) = Yc2-Yc1;
    Mat(3,1) = Zc2-Zc1;
    Mat = Mat/norm([Mat(1,1),Mat(2,1),Mat(3,1)]); % we have the first unit vector
    Mat(:,2) = cross([Mat(1,1),Mat(2,1),Mat(3,1)], [Xc3-Xc2,Yc3-Yc2,Zc3-Zc2]);
    Mat(:,2) = Mat(:,2)/norm([Mat(1,2),Mat(2,2),Mat(3,2)]); % we have the second unit vector
    Mat(:,3) = cross([Mat(1,1),Mat(2,1),Mat(3,1)], [Mat(1,2),Mat(2,2),Mat(3,2)]); % we have the 3° unit vector
endfunction
```

We call it with the command

```
[Mat_pe] = reference_system (Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1),Xc(i2),Yc(i2),Zc(i2),Xc(i3),Yc(i3),Zc(i3))
```

The new coordinates are then given by

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} = Mat_{pe}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x - x_c^{(i_1)} \\ y - y_c^{(i_1)} \\ z - z_c^{(i_1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

3.3.2 The ellipsoid of inertia containing the peptide

We search for the center of mass of the peptide. The coordinate of C_{pe} with respect to R' can be calculated from Eq. 13:

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad \begin{bmatrix} p_{C_{pe}} \\ q_{C_{pe}} \\ r_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix} = Mat_{pe}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x_{C_{pe}} - x_c^{(i_1)} \\ y_{C_{pe}} - y_c^{(i_1)} \\ z_{C_{pe}} - z_c^{(i_1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

We then consider the reference system R'' : C_{pe} ; s, t, v which is obtained by translation of the reference system R' so that its origin is on C_{pe} . We have

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} p_{C_{pe}} \\ q_{C_{pe}} \\ r_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix}$$

We then search for the moments of inertia of the peptide with respect to R'' : $C_{pe}; s, t, v$. This task is performed by the subroutine reported below, and the formulae used are the ones used for a system of material points (15). We have:

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad \begin{cases} J_s = \sum_i m_i (t_c^{(i)2} + v_c^{(i)2}) \\ J_t = \sum_i m_i (s_c^{(i)2} + v_c^{(i)2}) \\ J_v = \sum_i m_i (s_c^{(i)2} + t_c^{(i)2}) \\ J_{st} = \sum_i m_i s_c^{(i)} t_c^{(i)} \\ J_{sv} = \sum_i m_i s_c^{(i)} v_c^{(i)} \\ J_{tv} = \sum_i m_i t_c^{(i)} v_c^{(i)} \end{cases}$$

These moments of inertia are then conveniently stored as the elements of a matrix:

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad M_{pe} = \begin{bmatrix} J_s & -J_{st} & -J_{sv} \\ -J_{st} & J_t & -J_{tv} \\ -J_{sv} & -J_{tv} & J_v \end{bmatrix}$$

This task is performed by the subroutine `moments_of_inertia` (par. 3.2.3). The equation of the central ellipsoid of inertia with respect to R'' : $C_{pe}; s, t, v$ is then given by

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad [s \quad t \quad v] \begin{bmatrix} J_s & -J_{st} & -J_{sv} \\ -J_{st} & J_t & -J_{tv} \\ -J_{sv} & -J_{tv} & J_v \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} = \chi$$

or also $J_s s^2 + J_t t^2 + J_v v^2 - 2J_{st}st - 2J_{sv}sv - 2J_{tv}tv = \chi$. The coefficient χ defines the size of the ellipsoid and we are interested in finding the value that corresponds to the smaller possible ellipsoid that contains all the centers of mass of the amino acids of the peptide. This determination can be easily accomplished by considering that if P is a point on the surface of the ellipsoid and if α, β, γ are the direction cosines of $\overrightarrow{C_{pe}P}$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\overrightarrow{C_{pe}P}|^2 (J_s \alpha^2 + J_t \beta^2 + J_v \gamma^2 - 2J_{st} \alpha \beta - 2J_{sv} \alpha \gamma - 2J_{tv} \beta \gamma) &= \chi \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow |\overrightarrow{C_{pe}P}| &= \frac{\chi}{J_s \alpha^2 + J_t \beta^2 + J_v \gamma^2 - 2J_{st} \alpha \beta - 2J_{sv} \alpha \gamma - 2J_{tv} \beta \gamma} \end{aligned}$$

That said, let P_i the center of mass of the i^{th} amino acid of the peptide. We search for the smaller value χ such that

$$|\overrightarrow{C_{pe}P_i}| \leq \frac{\chi}{J_s \alpha^2 + J_t \beta^2 + J_v \gamma^2 - 2J_{st} \alpha \beta - 2J_{sv} \alpha \gamma - 2J_{tv} \beta \gamma}$$

This job is performed by the subroutine `ellipsoid_of_inertia` with the command:

```
[Chi,selection,product_Chi] = ellipsoid_of_inertia (aa_n_pe,Sc,Tc,Vc,1,Mpe,...
steps,aa_mass_pe,peptide_mass);
```

3.3.3 Central axes and moments of inertia

The search for the central axes of inertia can be accomplished by diagonalization of the matrix of inertia. More precisely, let Λ be the diagonal matrix such that

$$\text{Eq. 20} \quad \begin{bmatrix} J_s & -J_{st} & -J_{sv} \\ -J_{st} & J_t & -J_{tv} \\ -J_{sv} & -J_{tv} & J_v \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe} \Lambda_{pe} V_{pe}^T$$

then we have that

$$\text{Eq. 21} \quad \Lambda_{pe} = \begin{bmatrix} J_\alpha & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & J_\beta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & J_\gamma \end{bmatrix}$$

is the diagonal matrix whose diagonal elements are the major semi-axes of the central ellipsoid of inertia with respect to the reference system R''' : $C_{pe}; \alpha, \beta, \gamma$; and R''' is such that

$$\text{Eq. 22} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe}^T \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix}$$

In other words, the columns of V_{pe}^T are the coordinates of the unit vectors of R'' with respect to R''' , while the columns of V_{pe} are the coordinates with respect to R'' of the unit vectors of R''' . In other words, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 23} \quad \hat{\alpha} = [\hat{s} \quad \hat{t} \quad \hat{v}] V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\beta} = [\hat{s} \quad \hat{t} \quad \hat{v}] V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\gamma} = [\hat{s} \quad \hat{t} \quad \hat{v}] V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The matrices Λ_{pe} and V_{pe} are determined by the subroutine `central_axes`, which also determines the coordinates of all the centers of mass of the amino acids, with respect to R''' : $C_{pe}; \alpha, \beta, \gamma$. The subroutine is called by:

```
[semi_axis_alpha,semi_axis_beta,semi_axis_gamma,Vpe,lambda_pe,alphac,betac,gammac] = ...
central_axes(aa_n_pe,Mpe,Chi,selection,Sc,Tc,Vc)
```

3.3.4 Plotting the central axes of inertia

To plot the central axes of inertia with respect to R' : $O'; p, q, r$ we must find the components, with respect to R' of the unit vectors of R''' : $C_{pe}; \alpha, \beta, \gamma$, that we indicated $\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}$. From Eq. 22, we can write that the coordinates of $\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}$ with respect to R'' : $C_{pe}; s, t, v$ are given by

$$\text{Eq. 24} \quad \begin{bmatrix} s_\alpha \\ t_\alpha \\ v_\alpha \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} s_\beta \\ t_\beta \\ v_\beta \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} s_\gamma \\ t_\gamma \\ v_\gamma \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

respectively. Since R' and R'' have the same orientation of the axes, these are the components of $\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}$ with respect to R' too. In Figure 7 the three reference systems here discussed, are plotted along with the centers of mass of the amino acids of the peptide.

Figure 8. The peptide query-1-rank-1 on the left, compared with its central ellipsoid of inertia, scaled as the minimum ellipsoid that contains all the centers of mass of its amino acids.

3.3.5 Plotting the central ellipsoid of inertia

We plot the central ellipsoid of inertia, with respect to R' : O' ; p, q, r , to check that it contains the whole peptide, as it should. We use the subroutine `tilted_ellipsoid` called by:

```
tilted_ellipsoid(semi_axis_alpha,semi_axis_beta,semi_axis_gamma,Vpe,lambda_pe,Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe)
```

The subroutine is the following one. The result can be seen in Figure 8.

```
function tilted_ellipsoid(semi_axis_A,semi_axis_B,semi_axis_C,Vp,lambda_p,Xcp,Ycp,Zcp)
%
theta = linspace(0,2*pi,50); % polar coordinate
phi = linspace(0,pi,50); % polar coordinate
[theta,phi] = meshgrid(theta,phi);
A_ell = semi_axis_A*sin(phi).*cos(theta);
B_ell = semi_axis_B*sin(phi).*sin(theta);
C_ell = semi_axis_C*cos(phi);
ellipsoid = Vp*[A_ell(:)';B_ell(:)';C_ell(:)'];
X_ell = reshape(ellipsoid(1,:), size(A_ell));
Y_ell = reshape(ellipsoid(2,:), size(B_ell));
Z_ell = reshape(ellipsoid(3,:), size(C_ell));
X_ell = Xcp + X_ell;
Y_ell = Ycp + Y_ell;
Z_ell = Zcp + Z_ell;
surf(X_ell,Y_ell,Z_ell)
%
endfunction
```

3.4 Comparison between the peptide and the protein

Mat_{pe} had as columns the components of the unit vectors $\hat{p}, \hat{q}, \hat{r}$ with respect to the reference system of the PDB file ($O; x, y, z$), in the case of the protein I choose to store in the columns of Mat_p the coordinates of $\hat{p}, \hat{q}, \hat{r}$ with respect to the central axes of inertia, a, b, c . We use Eq. 25 to plot $O'; p, q, r$ along with the amino acids outside the ellipsoid of inertia of the protein, with respect to the central axes of inertia. The result is in Figure 9. The selection and the plotting of the amino acids outside the ellipsoid of inertia is performed by the following subroutine:

```
function inside_ellipsoid (aa_n_p,Ac,Bc,Cc,Chi_p,lambda_p,match,aa_name_p_2)
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
aa_dist(j) = sqrt(Ac(j)^2 + Bc(j)^2 + Cc(j)^2);
cos1(j) = Ac(j)/aa_dist(j);
cos2(j) = Bc(j)/aa_dist(j);
cos3(j) = Cc(j)/aa_dist(j);
v1 = [cos1(j),cos2(j),cos3(j)];
v2 = transpose(v1);
J_r(j) = v1*lambda_p*v2;
product_Chi(j) = (aa_dist(j)^2)*J_r(j);
endfor
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
if (product_Chi(j)>Chi_p)
if (ismember(j,match(1,:)))
plot3 (Ac(j), Bc(j), Cc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','y',...
'markeredgecolor','k')
else
plot3 (Ac(j), Bc(j), Cc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','b',...
'markeredgecolor','k')
endif
string1 = aa_name_p_2{j};
string2 = strcat(num2str(j),"-",string1(1),string1(2),string1(3));
hold on
text(Ac(j),Bc(j),Cc(j)+0.5,string2,"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold");
if (j<aa_n_p)
hold on
quiver3(Ac(j),Bc(j),Cc(j),Ac(j+1)-Ac(j),Bc(j+1)-Bc(j),Cc(j+1)-Cc(j),'-k',...
"maxheadsiz",0.1)
endif
hold on
endif
endfor
endfunction
```

The plotting of the reference system $O'; p, q, r$ is the results of the following instructions:

```
quiver3(Ac(i1),Bc(i1),Cc(i1),len*Mat_p(1,1),len*Mat_p(2,1),len*Mat_p(3,1),'-r',
"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Ac(i1)+len*Mat_p(1,1),Bc(i1)+len*Mat_p(2,1),Cc(i1)+len*Mat_p(3,1),...
"p","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold");
quiver3(Ac(i1),Bc(i1),Cc(i1),len*Mat_p(1,2),len*Mat_p(2,2),len*Mat_p(3,2),'-r',
"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Ac(i1)+len*Mat_p(1,2),Bc(i1)+len*Mat_p(2,2),Cc(i1)+len*Mat_p(3,2),...
"q","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold");
quiver3(Ac(i1),Bc(i1),Cc(i1),len*Mat_p(1,3),len*Mat_p(2,3),...
len*Mat_p(3,3),'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
```

```

text(Ac(i1)+len*Mat_p(1,3),Bc(i1)+len*Mat_p(2,3),Cc(i1)+...
len*Mat_p(3,3),"r","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold");
%
% title
%
title_str = strcat("protein: ",protein_name,"; mass: ",num2str(protein_mass),"Da ;...
length: ",num2str(aa_n_p)," aa","; F=",num2str(F));
title(title_str,"fontsize",15)
%
% axes
%
xlabel("A (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
ylabel("B (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
zlabel("C (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
axis("equal")

```

What about the components of the unit vectors of O' ; p, q, r with respect to O ; X, Y, Z ? By combining Eq. 10 and Eq. 25 we have:

$$\text{Eq. 27} \quad \begin{bmatrix} p_X \\ p_Y \\ p_Z \end{bmatrix} = V_p \text{Mat}_p \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} q_X \\ q_Y \\ q_Z \end{bmatrix} = V_p \text{Mat}_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} r_X \\ r_Y \\ r_Z \end{bmatrix} = V_p \text{Mat}_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The corresponding equations for the change of coordinates are

$$\text{Eq. 28} \quad \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_c(i_1) \\ Y_c(i_1) \\ Z_c(i_1) \end{bmatrix} + V_p \text{Mat}_p \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} = \text{Mat}_p^{-1} V_p^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} X - X_c(i_1) \\ Y - Y_c(i_1) \\ Z - Z_c(i_1) \end{bmatrix}$$

Note that, since O'' ; s, t, v is obtained as a rigid translation of O' ; p, q, r , the components of $\hat{s}, \hat{t}, \hat{v}$ are the same as those of $\hat{p}, \hat{q}, \hat{r}$:

$$\text{Eq. 29} \quad \begin{bmatrix} s_X \\ s_Y \\ s_Z \end{bmatrix} = V_p \text{Mat}_p \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} t_X \\ t_Y \\ t_Z \end{bmatrix} = V_p \text{Mat}_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} v_X \\ v_Y \\ v_Z \end{bmatrix} = V_p \text{Mat}_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The corresponding equations for the change of coordinates are

$$\text{Eq. 30} \quad \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_{pe}} \\ Y_{C_{pe}} \\ Z_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix} + V_p \text{Mat}_p \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} = \text{Mat}_p^{-1} V_p^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} X - X_{C_{pe}} \\ Y - Y_{C_{pe}} \\ Z - Z_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix}$$

where $X_{C_{pe}}, Y_{C_{pe}}, Z_{C_{pe}}$ must be determined. We have the coordinates of this point with respect to O' ; p, q, r (Eq. 15), then from Eq. 28 we have

$$\text{Eq. 31} \quad \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_{pe}} \\ Y_{C_{pe}} \\ Z_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_c(i_1) \\ Y_c(i_1) \\ Z_c(i_1) \end{bmatrix} + V_p \text{Mat}_p \begin{bmatrix} p_{C_{pe}} \\ q_{C_{pe}} \\ r_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix}$$

The passage of coordinates from α, β, γ to X, Y, Z can be obtained by combining Eq. 22 and Eq. 30 which give the change of coordinates from O''' ; α, β, γ to O ; X, Y, Z :

$$\text{Eq. 32} \quad \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_{pe}} \\ Y_{C_{pe}} \\ Z_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix} + V_p \text{Mat}_p V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe}^{-1} \text{Mat}_p^{-1} V_p^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} X - X_{C_{pe}} \\ Y - Y_{C_{pe}} \\ Z - Z_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore, the components of $\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}$ with respect to O ; X, Y, Z are given by

$$\text{Eq. 33} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_X \\ \alpha_Y \\ \alpha_Z \end{bmatrix} = V_p \text{Mat}_p V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} \beta_X \\ \beta_Y \\ \beta_Z \end{bmatrix} = V_p \text{Mat}_p V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_X \\ \gamma_Y \\ \gamma_Z \end{bmatrix} = V_p \text{Mat}_p V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

3.4.2 Plotting all the reference systems and the ellipsoid in the space of the protein

It seems useful, both as a check of the software and as a visual reminder of all the reference systems introduced for our analysis, to plot these elements in a single picture that can highlight their reciprocal positions in the space. We plot all these elements in the space of the protein, with respect to the axes O ; X, Y, Z . We plot the axes of C_{pe} ; ξ, η, ζ with the commands:

```
plot3([Xcp-len,Xcp+len],[Ycp,Ycp],[Zcp,Zcp],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"r")
text(Xcp+len+len/40,Ycp,Zcp,'\xi',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
hold on
plot3([Xcp,Xcp],[Ycp-len,Ycp+len],[Zcp,Zcp],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"r")
text(Xcp,Ycp+len+len/40,Zcp,'\eta',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
hold on
plot3([Xcp,Xcp],[Ycp,Ycp],[Zcp-len,Zcp+len],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"r")
text(Xcp,Ycp,Zcp+len+len/40,'\zeta',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
hold on
```

We plot the axes of C_{pe} ; a, b, c with the commands:

```
Av=Vp*transpose([len,0,0]);
Bv=Vp*transpose([0,len,0]);
Cv=Vp*transpose([0,0,len]);
%
plot3([Xcp-Av(1),Xcp+Av(1)],[Ycp-Av(2),Ycp+Av(2)],[Zcp-Av(3),Zcp+Av(3)],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"b")
text(Xcp+Av(1)+len/40,Ycp+Av(2)+len/40,Zcp+Av(3)+len/40,'a',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
hold on
plot3([Xcp-Bv(1),Xcp+Bv(1)],[Ycp-Bv(2),Ycp+Bv(2)],[Zcp-Bv(3),Zcp+Bv(3)],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"b")
text(Xcp+Bv(1)+len/40,Ycp+Bv(2)+len/40,Zcp+Bv(3)+len/40,'b',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
hold on
plot3([Xcp-Cv(1),Xcp+Cv(1)],[Ycp-Cv(2),Ycp+Cv(2)],[Zcp-Cv(3),Zcp+Cv(3)],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"b")
text(Xcp+Cv(1)+len/40,Ycp+Cv(2)+len/40,Zcp+Cv(3)+len/40,'c',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
```

To plot the axes O' ; p, q, r we make use of Eq. 27 and we write the instructions:

```
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,1);Mat_p(2,1);Mat_p(3,1)];
quiver3(Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1),v(1),v(2),v(3),'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xc(i1)+v(1),Yc(i1)+v(2),Zc(i1)+v(3),'p',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,2);Mat_p(2,2);Mat_p(3,2)];
quiver3(Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1),v(1),v(2),v(3),'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xc(i1)+v(1),Yc(i1)+v(2),Zc(i1)+v(3),'q',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
```

```
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,3);Mat_p(2,3);Mat_p(3,3)];
quiver3(Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1),v(1),v(2),v(3),'-r',"maxheadsiz"0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xc(i1)+v(1),Yc(i1)+v(2),Zc(i1)+v(3),"r","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
```

To plot the axes O'' ; s, t, v we use the instructions:

```
v2=[Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1)]+Vp*Mat_p*[Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe]';
Xcpe = v2(1);
Ycpe = v2(2);
Zcpe = v2(3);
%
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,1);Mat_p(2,1);Mat_p(3,1)];
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-b',"maxheadsiz"0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),"s","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,2);Mat_p(2,2);Mat_p(3,2)];
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-b',"maxheadsiz"0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),"t","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,3);Mat_p(2,3);Mat_p(3,3)];
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-b',"maxheadsiz"0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),"v","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
```

To plot the axes O''' ; α, β, γ we use the instructions:

```
v=len*Vp*Mat_p*Vpe*[1,0,0]';
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz"0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),'\{\alpha\}',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","y")
v=len*Vp*Mat_p*Vpe*[0,1,0]';
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz"0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),'\{\beta\}',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","y")
v=len*Vp*Mat_p*Vpe*[0,0,1]';
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz"0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),'\{\gamma\}',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","y")
```


Figure 10. All the reference systems involved, in the space of the protein. The central ellipsoid of inertia including the proportion F of the mass of the protein is plotted, as well as the central ellipsoid of inertia of the peptide, defined by the superimposition of the space of the peptide with the space of the protein, such that the reference system $O'; p, q, r$ of the space of the peptide coincides with the reference system of the space of the protein, with the same name.

To plot the ellipsoid of inertia of the protein that includes a proportion F of its mass, we call the subroutine `tilted_ellipsoid` (par. 3.3.5) with the line:

```
tilted_ellipsoid(semi_axis_A,semi_axis_B,semi_axis_C,Vp,lambda_p,Xcp,Ycp,Zcp)
```

To plot the ellipsoid of inertia of the peptide in the space of the protein, we need a matrix M_e whose column are the coordinates of $\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, \hat{\gamma}$ with respect to $O; X, Y, Z$. From Eq. 32 we have that the matrix we are searching for is $V_p \text{Mat}_p V_{pe}$. We also need the coordinates of C_{pe} with respect to $O; X, Y, Z$, but we have already calculated them in Eq. 31.

```
Me = Vp*Mat_p*Vpe;
tilted_ellipsoid(semi_axis_alpha,semi_axis_beta,semi_axis_gamma,Me,lambda_pe,Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe)
```

The result of this part of the script is

Figure 10. The ellipsoid of the peptide translated into the space of the protein is called *secondary ellipsoid*.

3.4.3 Isolation of the putative conformational B-cell epitope on the protein

We select only the amino acids of the protein that fall outside the central ellipsoid of inertia containing the proportion F of the mass of the protein and inside the central ellipsoid of inertia containing all the mass of the peptide. To perform this task, we use a subroutine that includes the instructions of `inside_ellipsoid` (par. 3.4.1). We pass to the subroutine the coordinates of the centers of mass of the amino acids with respect to $O; X, Y, Z$. Then we derive the coordinates in $C_p; a, b, c$ according to the following equation:

$$\text{Eq. 34} \quad \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix} = V_p^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} X - X_{C_p} \\ Y - Y_{C_p} \\ Z - Z_{C_p} \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_p} \\ Y_{C_p} \\ Z_{C_p} \end{bmatrix} + V_p \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix}$$

But we also need the coordinates with respect to $C_{pe}; \alpha, \beta, \gamma$ that can be obtained with Eq. 32. Then we can use the following subroutine.

```
function inside_ellipsoids (aa_n_p,Xc,Yc,Zc,Xcp,Ycp,Zcp,Vp,Chi_p,lambda_p,match,aa_name_p_2,...
Vpe,Mat_p,lambda_pe,Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,Chi_pe,i1)
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
v = inverse(Vp)*[Xc(j)-Xcp;Yc(j)-Ycp;Zc(j)-Zcp]
Ac(j) = v(1);
Bc(j) = v(2);
Cc(j) = v(3);
endfor
%
matrix = inverse(Vpe)*inverse(Mat_p)*inverse(Vp);
for j=1:aa_n_p
```

```

v = matrix*[Xc(j)-Xcpe;Yc(j)-Ycpe;Zc(j)-Zcpe]
alphac(j) = v(1);
betac(j) = v(2);
gammac(j) = v(3);
endfor
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
aa_dist(j) = sqrt(Ac(j)^2 + Bc(j)^2 + Cc(j)^2);
cos1(j) = Ac(j)/aa_dist(j);
cos2(j) = Bc(j)/aa_dist(j);
cos3(j) = Cc(j)/aa_dist(j);
v1 = [cos1(j),cos2(j),cos3(j)];
v2 = transpose(v1);
J_r(j) = v1*lambda_p*v2;
product_Chi_1(j) = (aa_dist(j)^2)*J_r(j);
endfor
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
aa_dist(j) = sqrt(alphac(j)^2 + betac(j)^2 + gammac(j)^2);
cos1(j) = alphac(j)/aa_dist(j);
cos2(j) = betac(j)/aa_dist(j);
cos3(j) = gammac(j)/aa_dist(j);
v1 = [cos1(j),cos2(j),cos3(j)];
v2 = transpose(v1);
J_r(j) = v1*lambda_pe*v2;
product_Chi_2(j) = (aa_dist(j)^2)*J_r(j);
endfor
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
v = inverse(Mat_p)*[Ac(j)-Ac(i1);Bc(j)-Bc(i1);Cc(j)-Cc(i1)]
Pc(j) = v(1);
Qc(j) = v(2);
Rc(j) = v(3);
endfor
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
if (and(product_Chi_1(j)>Chi_p,product_Chi_2(j)<=Chi_pe))
if (ismember(j,match(1,:)))
plot3 (Pc(j), Qc(j), Rc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','y',...
'markeredgecolor','k')
else
plot3 (Pc(j), Qc(j), Rc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','b',...
'markeredgecolor','k')
endif
string1 = aa_name_p_2{j};
string2 = strcat(num2str(j),"-",string1(1),string1(2),string1(3));
hold on
text(Pc(j),Qc(j),Rc(j)+0.5,string2,"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold");
if (j<aa_n_p)
hold on
quiver3(Pc(j),Qc(j),Rc(j),Pc(j+1)-Pc(j),Qc(j+1)-Qc(j),Rc(j+1)-Rc(j),'-k',...
"maxheadsize",0.1)
endif
hold on
endif
endfor
endfunction

```

Once the portion of the protein that is outside the primary ellipsoid (the one containing a fraction F of the mass of the protein) and inside the secondary ellipsoid (the one containing all the peptide) has been plotted (Figure 11), we can compare it with the peptide and make qualitative consideration on the similitude between these two special arrangements of amino acids. In this case, it seems possible to exclude a cross-reactivity between the two epitopes. The 3D plots generated by Octave can be rotated and manipulated in various ways, and this offers the possibility to have a complete understanding of the three-dimensional arrangement of the amino acids.

Figure 11. The peptide on the left, is compared with the region of the protein outside the primary ellipsoid and inside the secondary one, on the right. The reference system $O'; p, q, r$ is plotted in both cases. It seems possible to exclude a possible cross reactivity between the two epitopes.

3.5 Changes of coordinates, space of the peptide

$O; x, y, z \leftrightarrow O'; p, q, r$	$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = Mat_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} x_c^{(i_1)} \\ y_c^{(i_1)} \\ z_c^{(i_1)} \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} = Mat_{pe}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x - x_c^{(i_1)} \\ y - y_c^{(i_1)} \\ z - z_c^{(i_1)} \end{bmatrix}$
$O'; p, q, r \leftrightarrow O''; s, t, v$	$\begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} p_{C_{pe}} \\ q_{C_{pe}} \\ r_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} p_{C_{pe}} \\ q_{C_{pe}} \\ r_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix}$
$O''; s, t, v \leftrightarrow O'''; \alpha, \beta, \gamma$	$\begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix}$

3.6 Changes of coordinates, space of the protein

$O; X, Y, Z \leftrightarrow C_p; \xi, \eta, \zeta$	$\begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_p} \\ Y_{C_p} \\ Z_{C_p} \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_p} \\ Y_{C_p} \\ Z_{C_p} \end{bmatrix}$
--	---

$C_p; \xi, \eta, \zeta \leftrightarrow C_p; a, b, c$	$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix} = V_p^T \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix} = V_p \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix}$
$O; X, Y, Z \leftrightarrow C_p; a, b, c$	$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix} = V_p^T \begin{bmatrix} X - X_{C_p} \\ Y - Y_{C_p} \\ Z - Z_{C_p} \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_p} \\ Y_{C_p} \\ Z_{C_p} \end{bmatrix} + V_p \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix}$
$C_p; p, q, r \leftrightarrow C_p; a, b, c$	$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_c(i_1) \\ b_c(i_1) \\ c_c(i_1) \end{bmatrix} + Mat_p \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} = Mat_p^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} a - a_c(i_1) \\ b - b_c(i_1) \\ c - c_c(i_1) \end{bmatrix}$
$O; X, Y, Z \leftrightarrow O'; p, q, r$	$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_c(i_1) \\ Y_c(i_1) \\ Z_c(i_1) \end{bmatrix} + V_p Mat_p \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} = Mat_p^{-1} V_p^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} X - X_c(i_1) \\ Y - Y_c(i_1) \\ Z - Z_c(i_1) \end{bmatrix}$
$O; X, Y, Z \leftrightarrow C_{pe}; s, t, v$	$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_{pe}} \\ Y_{C_{pe}} \\ Z_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix} + V_p Mat_p \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \\ v \end{bmatrix} = Mat_p^{-1} V_p^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} X - X_{C_{pe}} \\ Y - Y_{C_{pe}} \\ Z - Z_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix}$
$O; X, Y, Z \leftrightarrow C_{pe}; \alpha, \beta, \gamma$	$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{C_{pe}} \\ Y_{C_{pe}} \\ Z_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix} + V_p Mat_p V_{pe} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow$ $\Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{bmatrix} = V_{pe}^{-1} Mat_p^{-1} V_p^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} X - X_{C_{pe}} \\ Y - Y_{C_{pe}} \\ Z - Z_{C_{pe}} \end{bmatrix}$

3.7 Main unit of the script

The main unit mainly performs task related to plotting, beside the calling of all the subroutine described in par. 3.

```
% file name = main_epitope_finder
% date of creation = 26/06/2023
%
%-----
% It reads PDB files previously converted into .xlsx and visualize them. It is
% assumed that a file contains a single protein. Each amino acid of the protein is
% represented as a ball with the average radius known for that amino acids, centered
% in the center of mass of the amino acid.
%-----
%
clear all
close all
pkg load io
pkg load statistics
%
%-----
% General settings
%-----
```

```

%
m = 1 % multiplicative factor for the radius of the amino acids
F = 0.2 % fraction of the mass of the protein included in the ellipsoid of inertia
N = 20; % dots for the circumferences of the spheres for the aas
Ne = 100; % dots for the ellipses of the ellipsoid of inertia
steps = 100; % number of attempts for the search of the ellipsoid including F of the mass
f = 0; % necessary for plotting
len = 50; % it is used to plot the axes of the reference systems
mul = 1.5; % multiplicative factor for the secondary ellipsoid
%
%-----
% Input settings
%-----
%
protein_name = "P42765-4C2J-A" % the name of the protein we are searching the epitope on
peptide_name = "query-1-rank-1" % the peptide that is a known epitope
match(1,:) = [72,73,74,75,76,77,78,79]; % the linear stretch of the protein that matches the one on the
peptide
match(2,:) = [5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12]; % the linear stretch of the peptide that matches the one on the protein
%
%-----
% Description of scalar variables
%-----
%
% atom_n_p - number of atoms of the protein
% atom_n_pe - number of atoms of the peptide
% aa_n_p - number of amino acids of the protein
% aa_n_pe - number of amino acids of the peptide
% protein_mass - mass of the protein
% peptide mass - mass of the peptide
% Xcp, Ycp, Zcp - coordinates of the center of mass of the protein in X,Y,Z coordinates
% Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe - coordinates of the center of mass of the peptide in X, Y, Z coordinates
%
%-----
% Description of arrays
%-----
%
% aa_radii - it contains the radius of each one of the 20 standard aminoacids (Angstrom)
% aa_name - it contains the name of each one of the 20 standard aminoacids
% atom_mass - it contains the atomic masses of the most common elements
% atom_name - it contains the names of the most common elements
%
%-----
% Description of arrays relative to the protein
%-----
%
% aa_name_p - for each atom of the protein, the name of the aa it belongs to (atom_n_p x 1)
% aa_name_p_2 - the names of the sequence of aas of the protein (aa_n_p x 1)
% aa_mass_p - the mass of each amino acid of the protein (aa_n_p x 1)
% aa_radii_p - the radii of the amino acids of the protein (aa_n_p x 1)
% atom_mass_p - the mass of the atoms of the protein (atom_n_p x 1)
% atom_name_p - contains the names of the atoms of the protein (atom_n_p x 1)
% atom_name_aa_p - as above, but with an add to the name for the role in the (atom_n_p x 1)
% X, Y, Z - coordinates of the atoms of the protein (atom_n_p x 1)
% Xc, Yc, Zc - coordinates of the centers of mass (CoM) of the aminoacids (aa_n_p x 1)
% Xic, Etac, Zetac - same as above but translated so to have the origin in Xcp,
% Ycp, Zcp (aa_n_p x 1)

```

```

% Ac, Bc, Cc - coordinates with respect to the central axes of inertia
% aa_dist - the distance of the CoM of each amino acid from the CoM of the protein (aa_n_p x 1)
% alpha, beta, gamma - the angular coefficients of the lines from the protein CoM
% to the aas CoMs (aa_n_p x 1)
% J_r - it is the protein moments of inertia with respect to the lines for the protein
% CoM and the aa CoMs (aa_n_p x 1)
% mass_inside - protein mass included in each one of the steps ellipsoid (steps x 1)
% F_inside - the percentage of protein mass included in each one of the steps ellipsoid (steps x 1)
% dist - the distance between two consecutive amino acids ((aa_n-1) x 1)
% Mat_p - its columns are the coordinates of the unit vectors of the reference system p,q,r with respect to
a,b,c
% Mp - matrix of inertia of the protein with respect to xi,eta,zeta
% Vp - its columns are the coordinates of a,b,c with respect to xi,eta,zeta
% lambda_p - matrix of inertia of the protein with respect to a,b,c
%
%-----
% Description of arrays relative to the peptide
%-----
%
% aa_name_pe - for each atom of the peptide, the name of the aa it belongs to (atom_n_pe x 1)
% atom_mass_pe - the mass of the atoms of the peptide (atom_n_pe x 1)
% aa_radii_pe - the radii of the amino acids of the peptide (aa_n_pe x 1)
% atom_name_pe - contains the names of the atoms of the peptide (atom_n_pe x 1)
% aa_name_pe_2 - the names of the sequence of aas of the protein (aa_n_pe x 1)
% atom_name_aa_pe - as above, but with an add to the name for the role in the amino acid (atom_n_pe x
1)
% X, Y, Z - coordinates of the atoms of the peptide (atom_n_pe x 1)
% Xc, Yc, Zc - coordinates of the centers of mass (CoM) of the aminoacids of the peptide (aa_n_pe x 1)
% Pc, Qc, Rc - as above, but with respect to the reference system p,q,r (aa_n_pe x 1)
% Sc, Tc, Vc - as above, but with respect to the reference system s,t,v (aa_n_pe x 1)
% Mat_pe - its columns are the coordinates of the unit vectors of the reference system p,q,r with respect to
x,y,z
% Mpe - matrix of inertia of the peptide with respect to s,t,v
% Vpe - its columns are the coordinates of alpha,beta,gamma with respect to s,t,v
% lambda_pe - matrix of inertia of the protein with respect to alpha,beta,gamma
%
%-----
% Preliminary input
%-----
%
[aa_radii,aa_name,atom_mass,atom_name] = input ()
%
%-----
% Input for the peptide
%-----
%
[atom_n_pe,atom_name_pe,atom_name_aa_pe,aa_name_pe,X,Y,Z] = input_sequence (peptide_name)
%
%-----
% Centers of mass and radius of each amino acid of the peptide
%-----
%
[counter,atom_mass_pe,aa_n_pe,Xc,Yc,Zc,aa_mass_pe,aa_radii_pe,aa_name_pe_2] = ...
centers_of_mass (atom_n_pe,atom_name_aa_pe,atom_name_pe,atom_name,atom_mass,X,Y,Z,...
aa_radii,aa_name_pe,aa_name);
%
%-----

```

```

% Coordinate system defined by the first three aas of the match on the peptide.
% The first two aas define the first unit vector and the first three define the plane
% that contains the first two unit vectors; the third unit vector can then be found.
%-----
%
i1=match(2,1); % index of the first aa of the match
i2=match(2,2); % index of the second aa of the match
i3=match(2,3); % index of the second aa of the match
[Mat_pe] = reference_system (Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1),Xc(i2),Yc(i2),Zc(i2),Xc(i3),Yc(i3),Zc(i3));
%
%-----
% We use p,q,r as new coordinate system
%-----
%
for j=1:aa_n_pe
    v = inverse(Mat_pe)*[Xc(j)-Xc(i1);Yc(j)-Yc(i1);Zc(j)-Zc(i1)];
    Pc(j) = v(1);
    Qc(j) = v(2);
    Rc(j) = v(3);
endfor
%
%-----
% We search for the moments of inertia of the peptide with respect to s,t,v, a
% reference system centered in the center of mass of the peptide and whose
% axes are parallel to p,q,r.
%-----
%
[peptide_mass,Sc,Tc,Vc,Mpe,Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe] = moments_of_inertia (aa_n_pe,aa_mass_pe,Pc,Qc,Rc);
%
%-----
% We search for the size of the ellipsoid of inertia
%-----
%
[Chi,selection,product_Chi] = ellipsoid_of_inertia
(aa_n_pe,Sc,Tc,Vc,1,Mpe,steps,aa_mass_pe,peptide_mass)
Chi_pe = mul*Chi(selection);
%
%-----
% We search for the central axes of inertia, for the semi-major axes of the
% ellipsoid, and for the coordinates of the amino acids with respect to the
% central axes
%-----
%
[semi_axis_alpha,semi_axis_beta,semi_axis_gamma,Vpe,lambda_pe,alphac,betac,gammac] = ...
central_axes (aa_n_pe,Mpe,Chi,selection,Sc,Tc,Vc)
%
%-----
% We plot the peptide with respect to p,q,r with all the reference systems
%-----
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
clear text % text is a cell previously defined, but we need the function text below
%
% plotting the spheres of the amino acids
%
for j=1:aa_n_pe

```

```

if (ismember(j,match(2,:)))
    plot3 (Pc(j), Qc(j), Rc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','y',...
        'markeredgecolor','k')
else
    plot3 (Pc(j), Qc(j), Rc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','r',...
        'markeredgecolor','k')
endif
string1 = aa_name_pe_2{j};
string2 = strcat(num2str(j),"-",string1(1),string1(2),string1(3));
hold on
text(Pc(j),Qc(j),Rc(j)+0.5,string2,"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold");
if (j<aa_n_pe)
    hold on
    quiver3(Pc(j),Qc(j),Rc(j),Pc(j+1)-Pc(j),Qc(j+1)-Qc(j),Rc(j+1)-Rc(j),'-k',...
        "maxheadsiz",0.1)
    endif
    hold on
endfor
%
% we add the unit vectors of the reference system p,q,r
%
quiver3(0,0,0,5,0,0,'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(5,0,0,"p","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
quiver3(0,0,0,0,5,0,'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(0,5,0,"q","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
quiver3(0,0,0,0,0,5,'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(0,0,5,"r","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
%
% we add the unit vectors of the reference system s,t,v
%
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,5,0,0,'-b',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe+5,Qcpe,Rcpe,"s","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,0,5,0,'-b',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe,Qcpe+5,Rcpe,"t","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,0,0,5,'-b',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe+5,"v","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
%
% we add the unit vectors of the reference system alpha,beta,gamma
%
v1=5*Vpe*[1;0;0];
v2=5*Vpe*[0;1;0];
v3=5*Vpe*[0;0;1];
%
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,v1(1),v1(2),v1(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe+v1(1),Qcpe+v1(2),Rcpe+v1(3),'\alpha',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","y")
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,v2(1),v2(2),v2(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe+v2(1),Qcpe+v2(2),Rcpe+v2(3),'\beta',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","y")
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,v3(1),v3(2),v3(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe+v3(1),Qcpe+v3(2),Rcpe+v3(3),'\gamma',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","y")
%
% title
%
title_str = strcat("peptide: ",peptide_name,"; mass: ",num2str(peptide_mass),"Da ;...
length: ",num2str(aa_n_pe)," aa");
title(title_str,"fontsize",15)
%
% axes

```

```

%
xlabel("P (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
ylabel("Q (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
zlabel("R (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
axis("equal")
%
%-----
% We plot the peptide with respect to p,q,r
%-----
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
clear text % text is a cell previously defined, but we need the function text below
%
% plotting the spheres of the amino acids
%
for j=1:aa_n_pe
    if (ismember(j,match(2,:)))
        plot3(Pc(j), Qc(j), Rc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','y',...
            'markeredgecolor','k')
    else
        plot3(Pc(j), Qc(j), Rc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','b',...
            'markeredgecolor','k')
    endif
    string1 = aa_name_pe_2{j};
    string2 = strcat(num2str(j),"-",string1(1),string1(2),string1(3));
    hold on
    text(Pc(j),Qc(j),Rc(j)+0.5,string2,"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold");
    if (j<aa_n_pe)
        hold on
        quiver3(Pc(j),Qc(j),Rc(j),Pc(j+1)-Pc(j),Qc(j+1)-Qc(j),Rc(j+1)-Rc(j),'-k',...
            "maxheadsize",0.1)
    endif
    hold on
endfor
%
% we add the unit vectors of the reference system p,q,r
%
quiver3(0,0,0,5,0,0,'-r',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(5,0,0,"p","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
quiver3(0,0,0,0,5,0,'-r',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(0,5,0,"q","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
quiver3(0,0,0,0,0,5,'-r',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(0,0,5,"r","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
%
% title
%
title_str = strcat("peptide: ",peptide_name,"; mass: ",num2str(peptide_mass),"Da ;...
length: ",num2str(aa_n_pe)," aa");
title(title_str,"fontsize",15)
%
% axes
%
xlabel("P (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
ylabel("Q (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
zlabel("R (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
axis("equal")

```

```

%
%-----
% We plot the peptide with respect to p,q,r and the ellipsoid that should contain
% it, as a check for the ellipsoid
%-----
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
clear text % text is a cell previously defined, but we need the function text below
%
% plotting the spheres of the amino acids
%
for j=1:aa_n_pe
    if (ismember(j,match(2,:)))
        plot3 (Pc(j), Qc(j), Rc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','y',...
            'markeredgecolor','k')
    else
        plot3 (Pc(j), Qc(j), Rc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','r',...
            'markeredgecolor','k')
    endif
    string1 = aa_name_pe_2{j};
    string2 = strcat(num2str(j),"-",string1(1),string1(2),string1(3));
    hold on
    text(Pc(j),Qc(j),Rc(j)+0.5,string2,"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold");
    if (j<aa_n_pe)
        hold on
        quiver3(Pc(j),Qc(j),Rc(j),Pc(j+1)-Pc(j),Qc(j+1)-Qc(j),Rc(j+1)-Rc(j),'-k',...
            "maxheadsize",0.1)
    endif
    hold on
endfor
%
% we add the unit vectors of the reference system p,q,r
%
quiver3(0,0,0,5,0,0,'-r',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(5,0,0,"p","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
quiver3(0,0,0,0,5,0,'-r',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(0,5,0,"q","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
quiver3(0,0,0,0,0,5,'-r',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(0,0,5,"r","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
%
% we add the unit vectors of the reference system s,t,v
%
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,5,0,0,'-b',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe+5,Qcpe,Rcpe,"s","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,0,5,0,'-b',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe,Qcpe+5,Rcpe,"t","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,0,0,5,'-b',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe+5,"v","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
%
% we add the unit vectors of the reference system alpha,beta,gamma
%
v1=5*Vpe*[1;0;0];
v2=5*Vpe*[0;1;0];
v3=5*Vpe*[0;0;1];
%
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,v1(1),v1(2),v1(3),'-y',"maxheadsize",0.1,"linewidth",2)

```

```

text(Pcpe+v1(1),Qcpe+v1(2),Rcpe+v1(3),{'\alpha'},"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,v2(1),v2(2),v2(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe+v2(1),Qcpe+v2(2),Rcpe+v2(3),{'\beta'},"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
quiver3(Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe,v3(1),v3(2),v3(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Pcpe+v3(1),Qcpe+v3(2),Rcpe+v3(3),{'\gamma'},"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
%
% title
%
title_str = strcat("peptide: ",peptide_name,"; mass: ",num2str(peptide_mass),"Da ;...
length: ",num2str(aa_n_pe)," aa");
title(title_str,"fontsize",15)
%
% axes
%
xlabel("P (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
ylabel("Q (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
zlabel("R (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
axis("equal")
%
% plotting the ellipsoid of inertia containing the peptide
%
tilted_ellipsoid(semi_axis_alpha,semi_axis_beta,semi_axis_gamma,Vpe,lambda_pe,Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe)
%
%-----
% Input for the protein
%-----
%
[atom_n_p,atom_name_p,atom_name_aa_p,aa_name_p,X,Y,Z] = input_sequence (protein_name)
%
%-----
% Centers of mass and radius of each amino acid of the protein
%-----
%
[counter,atom_mass_p,aa_n_p,Xc,Yc,Zc,aa_mass_p,aa_radii_p,aa_name_p_2] = ...
centers_of_mass (atom_n_p,atom_name_aa_p,atom_name_p,atom_name,atom_mass,X,Y,Z,...
aa_radii,aa_name_p,aa_name);
%
% it calculates the distances between the CoMs of two consequent amino acids
%
for j=1:aa_n_p - 1
    dist(j) = sqrt( (Xc(j+1)-Xc(j))^2 + (Yc(j+1)-Yc(j))^2 + (Zc(j+1)-Zc(j))^2 );
endfor
%
%-----
% We search for the moments of inertia of the protein
%-----
%
[protein_mass,Xic,Etac,Zetac,Mp,Xcp,Ycp,Zcp] = moments_of_inertia (aa_n_p,aa_mass_p,Xc,Yc,Zc);
%
%-----
% We search for the size of the ellipsoid of inertia
%-----
%
[Chi,selection,product_Chi] = ellipsoid_of_inertia (aa_n_p,Xic,Etac,Zetac,F,Mp,...
steps,aa_mass_p,protein_mass);
Chi_p = Chi(selection);
%

```

```

%-----
% We search for the central axes of inertia, for the semi-major axes of the
% ellipsoid, and for the coordinates of the amino acids with respect to the
% central axes
%-----
%
[semi_axis_A,semi_axis_B,semi_axis_C,Vp,lambda_p,Ac,Bc,Cc] = ...
central_axes(aa_n_p,Mp,Chi,selection,Xic,Etac,Zetac)
%
%-----
% Coordinate system defined by the first three aas of the match on the protein.
% The first two aas define the first unit vector and the first three define the plane
% that contains the first two unit vectors; the third unit vector can then be found.
%-----
%
i1=match(1,1); % index of the first aa of the match
i2=match(1,2); % index of the second aa of the match
i3=match(1,3); % index of the second aa of the match
[Mat_p] = reference_system (Ac(i1),Bc(i1),Cc(i1),Ac(i2),Bc(i2),Cc(i2),Ac(i3),Bc(i3),Cc(i3));
%
%-----
% We plot the protein in the original coordinate system
%-----
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
clear text % text is a cell previously defined, but we need the function text below
%
% plotting the spheres of the amino acids
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
    ellipsoid (Xc(j), Yc(j), Zc(j), m*aa_rad_ii_p(j), m*aa_rad_ii_p(j), m*aa_rad_ii_p(j), N);
    string1 = aa_name_p_2{j};
    string2 = strcat(num2str(j),"-",string1(1),string1(2),string1(3));
    hold on
    text(Xc(j),Yc(j),Zc(j)+2*m*aa_rad_ii_p(j),string2,"fontsize",15);
    if (j<aa_n_p)
        hold on
        quiver3(Xc(j),Yc(j),Zc(j),Xc(j+1)-Xc(j),Yc(j+1)-Yc(j),Zc(j+1)-Zc(j),'-k',...
            "maxheadsize",0.1)
    endif
    if (j>aa_n_p)
        break
    endif
    hold on
endfor
%
% title
%
title_str = strcat("protein: ",protein_name,"; mass: ",num2str(protein_mass),"Da ;...
length: ",num2str(aa_n_p)," aa");
title(title_str,"fontsize",15)
%
% axes
%
xlabel("X (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
ylabel("Y (angstrom)","fontsize",15)

```

```

xlabel("Z (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
plot_range_1 = [min(Xc)-5,max(Xc)+5,min(Yc)-5,max(Yc)+5,min(Zc)-5,max(Zc)+5];
axis(plot_range_1,"equal")
%
%-----
% We plot the protein with respect to central axes of inertia along with the
% central ellipsoid of inertia
%-----
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
%
% plotting the spheres of the amino acids
%
for j=1:aa_n_p
    if (product_Chi(j)>Chi(selection))
        if (ismember(j,match(1,:)))
            plot3 (Ac(j), Bc(j), Cc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','y',...
                'markeredgecolor','k')
        else
            plot3 (Ac(j), Bc(j), Cc(j),'o','markersize',6,'markerfacecolor','r',...
                'markeredgecolor','k')
        endif
        string1 = aa_name_p_2{j};
        string2 = strcat(num2str(j),"-",string1(1),string1(2),string1(3));
        hold on
        text(Ac(j),Bc(j),Cc(j)+0.5,string2,"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold");
        if (j<aa_n_p)
            hold on
            quiver3(Ac(j),Bc(j),Cc(j),Ac(j+1)-Ac(j),Bc(j+1)-Bc(j),Cc(j+1)-Cc(j),'-k',...
                "maxheadsiz",0.1)
        endif
        hold on
    endif
endfor
%
% ellipsoid
%
ellipsoid (0,0,0,semi_axis_A,semi_axis_B,semi_axis_C,Ne);
%
% title
%
title_str = strcat("protein: ",protein_name,"; mass: ",num2str(protein_mass),"Da ;...
length: ",num2str(aa_n_p)," aa"; F=",num2str(F));
title(title_str,"fontsize",15)
%
% axes
%
xlabel("A (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
ylabel("B (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
zlabel("C (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
plot_range_2 = [min(Ac)-5,max(Ac)+5,min(Bc)-5,max(Bc)+5,min(Cc)-5,max(Cc)+5];
axis(plot_range_2,"equal")
%
%-----
% We plot the protein with respect to central axes of inertia, but only the amino
% acids that fall outside the central ellipsoid of inertia, with also axes p,q,r

```

```

%-----
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
%
% plotting the spheres of the amino acids
%
inside_ellipsoid (aa_n_p,Ac,Bc,Cc,Chi_p,lambda_p,match,aa_name_p_2)
%
% we add the unit vectors of the reference system on the match
%
quiver3(Ac(i1),Bc(i1),Cc(i1),len*Mat_p(1,1),len*Mat_p(2,1),len*Mat_p(3,1),'-
r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Ac(i1)+len*Mat_p(1,1),Bc(i1)+len*Mat_p(2,1),Cc(i1)+len*Mat_p(3,1),"p","fontsize",17,"fontweight","b
old","color","r");
quiver3(Ac(i1),Bc(i1),Cc(i1),len*Mat_p(1,2),len*Mat_p(2,2),len*Mat_p(3,2),'-
r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Ac(i1)+len*Mat_p(1,2),Bc(i1)+len*Mat_p(2,2),Cc(i1)+len*Mat_p(3,2),"q","fontsize",17,"fontweight","b
old","color","r");
quiver3(Ac(i1),Bc(i1),Cc(i1),len*Mat_p(1,3),len*Mat_p(2,3),len*Mat_p(3,3),'-
r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(Ac(i1)+len*Mat_p(1,3),Bc(i1)+len*Mat_p(2,3),Cc(i1)+len*Mat_p(3,3),"r","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bo
ld","color","r");
%
% title
%
title_str = strcat("protein: ",protein_name,"; mass: ",num2str(protein_mass),"Da ;...
length: ",num2str(aa_n_p)," aa","; F=",num2str(F));
title(title_str,"fontsize",15)
%
% axes
%
xlabel("A (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
ylabel("B (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
zlabel("C (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
axis("equal")
%
%-----
% We plot the distribution of the distance between the CoM of two consequent
% amino acids
%-----
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
hist (dist, 20);
xlabel ("distance (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
ylabel ("couples of consecutive amino acids","fontsize",15)
title("distance between two consecutive amino acids","fontsize",15)
%
%-----
% We plot the reference systems and the ellipsoid of the protein with respect to x,y,z
%-----
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
%
% plotting axes X, Y, Z

```

```

%
plot3([-len,len],[0,0],[0,0],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"k")
text(len+len/40,0,0,"X","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
hold on
plot3([0,0],[-len,len],[0,0],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"k")
text(0,len+len/40,0,"Y","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
hold on
plot3([0,0],[0,0],[-len,len],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"k")
text(0,0,len+len/40,"Z","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold")
hold on
%
% plotting axes xi, eta, zeta
%
plot3([Xcp-len,Xcp+len],[Ycp,Ycp],[Zcp,Zcp],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"r")
text(Xcp+len+len/40,Ycp,Zcp,'\xi',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
hold on
plot3([Xcp,Xcp],[Ycp-len,Ycp+len],[Zcp,Zcp],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"r")
text(Xcp,Ycp+len+len/40,Zcp,'\eta',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
hold on
plot3([Xcp,Xcp],[Ycp,Ycp],[Zcp-len,Zcp+len],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"r")
text(Xcp,Ycp,Zcp+len+len/40,'\zeta',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
hold on
%
% plotting axes a, b, c
%
Av=Vp*transpose([len,0,0]);
Bv=Vp*transpose([0,len,0]);
Cv=Vp*transpose([0,0,len]);
%
plot3([Xcp-Av(1),Xcp+Av(1)],[Ycp-Av(2),Ycp+Av(2)],[Zcp-Av(3),Zcp+Av(3)],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"b")
text(Xcp+Av(1)+len/40,Ycp+Av(2)+len/40,Zcp+Av(3)+len/40,'a',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
)
hold on
plot3([Xcp-Bv(1),Xcp+Bv(1)],[Ycp-Bv(2),Ycp+Bv(2)],[Zcp-Bv(3),Zcp+Bv(3)],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"b")
text(Xcp+Bv(1)+len/40,Ycp+Bv(2)+len/40,Zcp+Bv(3)+len/40,'b',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
)
hold on
plot3([Xcp-Cv(1),Xcp+Cv(1)],[Ycp-Cv(2),Ycp+Cv(2)],[Zcp-Cv(3),Zcp+Cv(3)],"linestyle","-","linewidth",1,"b")
text(Xcp+Cv(1)+len/40,Ycp+Cv(2)+len/40,Zcp+Cv(3)+len/40,'c',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
%
% we add the axes of the reference system p,q,r
%
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,1);Mat_p(2,1);Mat_p(3,1)];
quiver3(Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1),v(1),v(2),v(3),'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xc(i1)+v(1),Yc(i1)+v(2),Zc(i1)+v(3),"p","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,2);Mat_p(2,2);Mat_p(3,2)];
quiver3(Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1),v(1),v(2),v(3),'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xc(i1)+v(1),Yc(i1)+v(2),Zc(i1)+v(3),"q","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,3);Mat_p(2,3);Mat_p(3,3)];
quiver3(Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1),v(1),v(2),v(3),'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xc(i1)+v(1),Yc(i1)+v(2),Zc(i1)+v(3),"r","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r")
%
% we add the axes of the reference system s,t,v
%
v2=[Xc(i1),Yc(i1),Zc(i1)]'+Vp*Mat_p*[Pcpe,Qcpe,Rcpe]';
Xcpe = v2(1);
Ycpe = v2(2);

```

```

Zcpe = v2(3);
%
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,1);Mat_p(2,1);Mat_p(3,1)];
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-b',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),"s","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,2);Mat_p(2,2);Mat_p(3,2)];
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-b',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),"t","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
v=len*Vp*[Mat_p(1,3);Mat_p(2,3);Mat_p(3,3)];
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-b',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),"v","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","b")
%
% we add the axes of the reference system alpha,beta,gamma
%
v=len*Vp*Mat_p*Vpe*[1,0,0]';
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),'\alpha',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","y")
v=len*Vp*Mat_p*Vpe*[0,1,0]';
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),'\beta',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","y")
v=len*Vp*Mat_p*Vpe*[0,0,1]';
quiver3(Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,v(1),v(2),v(3),'-y',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",1)
text(Xcpe+v(1),Ycpe+v(2),Zcpe+v(3),'\gamma',"fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","y")
%
% plotting the ellipsoid of inertia of the protein with index F
%
tilted_ellipsoid(semi_axis_A,semi_axis_B,semi_axis_C,Vp,lambda_p,Xcp,Ycp,Zcp)
%
% plotting the ellipsoid of inertia of the protein with index F
%
Me = Vp*Mat_p*Vpe;
tilted_ellipsoid(semi_axis_alpha,semi_axis_beta,semi_axis_gamma,Me,lambda_pe,Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe)
%
set(gcf, 'renderer', 'painters'); % Use the 'painters' renderer for better quality
%
% axes
%
axis("equal")
%
%-----
% We plot the protein with respect to central axes of inertia, but only the amino
% acids that fall outside the central ellipsoid of inertia, and inside the
% secondary ellipsoid of inertia
%-----
%
f = f + 1;
figure(f)
%
% plotting the spheres of the amino acids
%
inside_ellipsoids(aa_n_p,Xc,Yc,Zc,Xcp,Ycp,Zcp,Vp,Chi_p,lambda_p,match,aa_name_p_2,...
Vpe,Mat_p,lambda_pe,Xcpe,Ycpe,Zcpe,Chi_pe,i1)
%
% we add the unit vectors of the reference system on the match
%
len=5;
quiver3(0,0,0,len,0,0,'-r',"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)

```

```

text(len,0,0,"p","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r");
quiver3(0,0,0,0,len,0,-r,"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(0,len,0,"q","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r");
quiver3(0,0,0,0,0,len,-r,"maxheadsiz",0.1,"linewidth",2)
text(0,0,len,"r","fontsize",17,"fontweight","bold","color","r");
%
% title
%
title_str = strcat("protein: ",protein_name,"; mass: ",num2str(protein_mass),"Da ;...
length: ",num2str(aa_n_p)," aa","; F=",num2str(F));
title(title_str,"fontsize",15)
%
% axes
%
xlabel("P (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
ylabel("Q (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
zlabel("R (angstrom)","fontsize",15)
axis("equal")

```

sequence	protein			start_p	stop_p	query	start_q	stop_q	ElliPro
GLRVQY	16969	Q8IWF2	AF-Q8IWF2-F1	137	142	1	8	13	N
PQLQSS	3604	Q14497	AF-O14497-F1	509	514	2	9	14	Y
PQLQSS	14465	Q8NDX9	AF-Q8NDX9-F1	110	115	2	9	14	N
LQSSGS	10675	Q9BQI6	AF-Q9BQ16-F1	691	696	2	11	16	N
RQRVLS	10191	Q9H3R0	AF-Q9H3R0-F1	1022	1027	3	5	10	N
RQRVLS	12175	Q96RW7	?	4124	4129	3	5	10	?
QRVLS	12828	P06401	AF-P06401-F1	158	163	3	6	11	Y
VLSPVL	18847	Q6UXD7	AF-Q6UXD7-F1	180	185	3	8	13	N
SPVLGA	11050	Q53ET0	AF-Q53ET0-F1	408	413	3	10	15	Y
SPVLGA	16094	Q9NZL9	AF-Q9NZL9-F1	282	287	3	10	15	Y
SPVLGA	18052	Q6UWL6	AF-Q6UWL6-F1	266	271	3	10	15	N
RVLSEQ	11796	Q9UPN3	?	1310	1315	4	4	9	?
VLSEQD	4979	Q92834	AF-Q92834-F1	459	464	4	5	10	Y
HVRVLS	14950	Q32NB8	AF-Q32NB8-F1	96	101	5	3	8	N
RVLSQK	3279	Q9BVJ6	AF-Q9BVJ6-F1	461	466	5	5	10	N
RVLSQK	8749	Q56NI9	AF-Q56NI9-F1	193	198	5	5	10	N
RVLSQK	10430	P49914	3HXT	34	39	5	5	10	N
VLSQKR	1041	Q14315	?	76	81	5	6	11	?
VLSQKR	5996	Q9Y337	AF-Q9Y337-F1	211	216	5	6	11	Y
VLSQKR	10817	Q75369	AF-O75369-F1	56	61	5	6	11	N
LSQKRP	5584	Q9BT81	AF-Q9BT81-F1	88	93	5	7	12	N
LSQKRP	7336	P51508	AF-P51508-F1	184	189	5	7	12	N
SQKRPL	15108	A8MZ97	AF-A8MZ97-F1	150	155	5	8	13	N
SQKRPL	19558	Q7Z6Z7	?	3695	3700	5	8	13	Y
ALHLHR	16192	Q9P225	?	1792	1797	6	1	6	?
HRHVLE	625	P50851	?	1270	1275	6	5	10	?
RHVLES	213	Q75444	AF-O75444-F1	313	318	6	6	11	N
ESQVNS	15822	P11717	AF-P11717-F1	1478	1483	6	10	15	N
SQVNSL	13148	Q5HYK7	AF-Q5HYK7-F1	656	661	6	11	16	N

Table 4. Matches of 6 amino acids between the query sequences and the human proteome [UP000005640](#). The response of ElliProt is Yes (Y) only if the predicted epitope includes all the 6 amino acids of the match.

4 Running the pipeline on matches of six amino acids

If we run again the script of par. 2.2 this time asking for matches of only 6 amino acids, we get 30 matches, after the removal of the 4 that corresponds to those already collected in Table 2. I report the matches in Table 4, with also an indication of the structure considered and of the response of ElliPro on the inclusion of the match in a possible epitope of the structure. When a complete experimental structure is not available, I use the one predicted by AlphaFold2. In what follows I discuss only the matches that are predicted to be part of an epitope by ElliPro.

Figure 12. The positions 509-515 of protein O14497 are surface exposed (left) and are predicted to be part of an epitope, by ElliPro.

Figure 13. Peptide 2 on the left, and the region of protein O14497 isolated by the secondary ellipsoid, on the right.

4.1 Query sequence 2

4.1.1 Protein Q8IWF2

The match at position 509-515 of the sequence is surface exposed and is also predicted to be part of a conformational epitope, by ElliPro (Figure 12). The comparison by main_epitope_finder shows that there is no apparent cross-reactivity between the query sequence 2 (peptide 2 of Table 1) and the region isolated by the secondary ellipsoid (with a factor scale of 2) on protein O14497 (Figure 13).

Figure 14. The positions 158-164 of protein P06401 are surface exposed (left) and are predicted to be part of an epitope, by ElliPro.

Figure 15. Peptide 3 on the left, and the region of protein P06401 isolated by the secondary ellipsoid, on the right.

4.2 Query sequence 3

4.2.1 Protein P06401

The match at position 158-164 of the sequence is surface exposed and is also predicted to be part of a conformation epitope, by ElliPro (Figure 14). The comparison by main_epitope_finder shows that there is no apparent cross-reactivity between the query sequence 2 (peptide 3 of Table 1) and the region isolated by the secondary ellipsoid (with a factor scale of 2) on protein P06401 (Figure 15).

Figure 16. The positions 408-413 of protein Q53ET0 are surface exposed (left) and are predicted to be part of an epitope, by ElliPro.

Figure 17. Peptide 3 on the left, and the region of protein Q53ET0 isolated by the secondary ellipsoid, on the right.

4.2.2 Protein Q53ET0

The match at position 408-413 of the sequence is surface exposed and is also predicted to be part of a conformation epitope, by ElliPro (Figure 16). The comparison by main_epitope_finder shows that there is no apparent cross-reactivity between the query

sequence 2 (peptide 3 of Table 1) and the region isolated by the secondary ellipsoid (with a factor scale of 2) on protein Q53ET0 (Figure 17).

4.2.3 Protein Q9NZL9

The match at position 282-287 of the sequence is surface exposed and is also predicted to be part of a conformation epitope, by ElliPro (Figure 18). The comparison by main_epitope_finder shows that there is no apparent cross-reactivity between the query sequence 2 (peptide 3 of Table 1) and the region isolated by the secondary ellipsoid (with a factor scale of 2) on protein Q9NZL9 (Figure 19).

Figure 18. The positions 282-287 of protein Q9NZL9 are surface exposed (left) and are predicted to be part of an epitope, by ElliPro.

Figure 19. Peptide 3 on the left, and the region of protein Q9NZL9 isolated by the secondary ellipsoid, on the right.

4.3 Query sequence 4

4.3.1 Protein Q92834

The match at position 459-464 of the sequence is surface exposed and is also predicted to be part of a conformational epitope, by ElliPro. No cross-reactivity seems possible (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Peptide 4 on the left, and the region of protein Q92834 isolated by the secondary ellipsoid, on the right.

Figure 21. Peptide 5 on the left, and the region of protein Q9Y337 isolated by the secondary ellipsoid, on the right.

4.4 Query sequence 5

4.4.1 Protein Q9Y337

The match at position 211-216 of the sequence is surface exposed and is also predicted to be part of a conformation epitope, by ElliPro. No cross-reactivity seems possible (Figure 21).

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